

Lepidoptera

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Lepidoptera: Neopseustidae

Neopseustis meyricki

Neopseustis meyricki Hering, 1925

Agaristidae: *Hecatesia fenestrata*

Australia

Whistling Moth

Whistling Moth

Agaristidae: *Hecatesia fenestrata* (Boisduval)

Australia E.

FW

$d = 12 \text{ mm}$

1978 Nature 4945 W.J. Bailey

resonating area in the same place as some ? sound ? producing area of Synemou (p. 827)
veins based on Permian Trichoptera

Mnesarchaeoidea (sister of Hepialoidea)

Fraus minima Nielsen & Kristensen 1984

Endemic Australia

HEPIALIDAE: *Oxycanus diremptus* (Walker)

in HW:
AA 1+2 is reduced!

CP in Neuroptera shows that "humeral vein" is recurrent CP: which fused with anterior wing margin

FW Hepialidae: *Trictena argentata*

Carnegie, Pittsburg

HW

Hepialidae: *Trictena argentata*

Mnesarchaeoidea (sister of Hepialoidea)

Fraus minima Nielsen & Kristensen 1984

Endemic Australia

FW Neopseustidae: *Neopseustis meyricki* Hering, 1925 rare, primitive Taiwan

Primitive features:

- FW
- 1) ScP forked
 - 2) arcus is a cross-vein (not a fusion)
 - 3) CuA seems primitively forked!

OXYCANUS
DIREMUS WALTER

Neopseustis meyricki Hering 1925

rare, primitive, Taiwan

HW

